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A Creative Folio

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Little Experience, Big Lessons from My Field Study Experience

During my field study, I observed various classes, including English, Math, Science, and Filipino, in a Grade 6 classroom for several weeks. This experience allowed me to observe actual teaching practices and provided a clearer view of how lessons are delivered in real classroom settings. I noticed that each subject required different approaches, depending on the topic and learners' needs. Through this exposure, I gained practical knowledge about both teaching strategies and classroom management.

I observed that teachers used a variety of methods to help students better understand the lessons. These included discussions, group reporting, and role-playing activities. Each strategy encouraged participation and allowed students to express their ideas. I saw how these approaches made the classroom more interactive and helped students become more confident in sharing their thoughts. It also became clear to me that when students are actively involved, they tend to understand and retain the lesson better.

After each lesson, teachers would give activities or exercises to assess whether the students had understood the topic. These activities also allowed students to apply what they had learned. I realized that assessment is not only for grading but also for guiding both the teacher and the students on what needs improvement. Aside from observation, I was also allowed to assist my cooperating teachers. I helped write the SF10, checked test papers, and handled Grade 4, Aral tutees. These tasks helped me understand that teaching involves many responsibilities beyond classroom instruction.

While observing, I noticed that some students were shy and had difficulty answering questions. However, the teachers remained patient and supportive. They guided the students step by step, gave clear instructions, and encouraged them to participate. This showed me the importance of creating a safe and supportive learning environment where students feel comfortable making mistakes and trying again.

From this experience, I learned that teaching goes beyond simply explaining lessons. It requires patience, creativity, and a genuine understanding of students' needs. I also realized that teachers play an important role not only in developing students' academic skills but also in shaping their character and confidence. This field study strengthened my interest in the teaching profession and helped me appreciate the real challenges and rewards of being an educator.